

Contemporary relevance of Gandhian Thoughts in today's society

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Introduction:

The paper is an attempt to discuss how the Gandhian realities are applicable today. Mahatma Gandhiji the Father of Nation emphasis on humanity, tolerance, self-discipline and communal harmony could transform society and mould it in the right direction. Today in world plagued by the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, menace of global terrorism, global warming and climate change owing the environmental destructions and ecological imbalances, growing incidence of poverty related death as followed of liberalization, privatization and Globalization (LPG). Gandhi as well as his philosophy appears relevant for every people love him and like to follow his philosophy as proved from the phenomenal success of Bollywood Block buster “Lage Raho Munna Bhai” which brought down the philosophy of Gandhi from the papers of history books to the common masses in the term of Gandhigiri. The Gandhigiri is a based on Satyagraha, non-violence and truth to help ordinary people to solve their problems. So we focus some aspects of Gandhian thought and its relevance in today's life through this paper.

Gandhian Thoughts and Communal harmony:

Today the world is witnessing more communal clashes across the globe. The world facing the problem of communal clashes to handle the problem we just focus the Gandhi and his philosophy. Gandhi never wished to see the people to be a communal bigot a rather he pleaded for the humanization of knowledge for immunization against the ideas of distrust among the communities of the nation and the nationalities of the world. He wanted to take the country from areas of hostility in to areas of harmony of faiths. Gandhi valued communal harmony and asked the people to tolerate other community as their brothers and sisters. He instead to give the communal harmony highest priority as a key to its progress and national integration.

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Gandhian Thoughts and Rural Development:

The ultimate goal of Gandhi was a non-violent decentralized democratic political order from village republic to international field. Gandhi thought that every village must be most democratically organized and must be vested with enough powers to settle all or nearly all problems affecting the village after the independence India is a continuous search for realizing Gandhi's concept of gram Swarajya through its various rural realizing Gandhi's concept of Gram Swarajya through its various rural development programme like PURA a model of rural development, Bharat Nirman Yojana for strengthen the governance process of rural India by developing political as well as financial power to the Gram Panchayat to give tribute to Gandhiji by the historic rural employment guarantee to give tribute to Gandhiji by the historic rural employment guarantee act Sept.2005. We sow the reflection of Gandhiji's concern in this programme. Thus, this reaffirmed the relevance of Gandhian through as India is still looking ahead to achieve the target set by Gandhiji in his model of Gram Swarajya.

Gandhian Thoughts and Education:

Gandhiji's education is for all and one for the young and old for boys and girls more girls than boys. This aspect to Gandhian thought got a vindication when in 2002 the government enacted 86th constitutional Amendment act which made education as a fundamental right. The government is also trying to universalize the primary education through the various programmes like National Literacy Mission, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Mid-Day Meal Scheme, National Programmes for education of Girls, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidhyalaya etc. for implement thoughts of Gandhiji's education is for all.

Gandhian Thoughts and World Peace:

Today in the era of Globe terrorism, nuclear weapon and weapons of mass-destruction the only philosophy or rather way of life that ensures our longevity on earth in Gandhian through of non-violence. Gandhi ridiculed the ideas of war to end the war. He maintained war do not end anything except humanity. Therefore, if humanity is to survive, we must go back to Gandhi and bring peace to the 21st century.

Conclusion:

We discuss most of the issues in priest world. After this discussion we have got a conclusion that we need the philosophy of Gandhian thoughts to save the human civilization from various problems. Today

not only India but also world need the help of Gandhian through to solved various problems and establishment of peace so it is the right time to elaborate the social, economical, political thoughts of Mahatma by Gandhian followers.

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